

TAICHI RESERVOIR - A RESERVOIR STRUCTURE TO SOLVE SEDIMENTATION ACCUMULATION PROBLEM

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Abstract:

For reservoirs, it is necessary to deal with the sedimentation accumulation problem because sedimentation accumulation will greatly reduce the usable volume of the reservoir and cause the reservoir to contain much less water than designed. This article proposes the structure of Taichi reservoir. Taichi reservoir is a reservoir which uses the shape of Taichi as a primary structure. This reservoir structure includes the sedimentation tank and the main body. This structure can be effective in solving sedimentation accumulation problem for reservoirs. In addition, the Taichi reservoir is not difficult to design and not costly to build. Taichi reservoir is more useful when the incoming water of a reservoir contains more sedimentation matters.

Key Words: Reservoir; Sedimentation; Dam; Taichi; Accumulation; Muddy; Foreign Matters; Water; Water Conservancy; Water Resource; River

Main Text:

Reservoirs are bodies of stored fresh water that typically form behind dams. They are a critical water source, supplying farms with irrigation and providing potable water to people and homes. Increasingly, they are also an important component of outdoor, water-based recreation.

As rivers flow, they naturally carry along sediment (clay, silt, sand, and gravel). When rivers are dammed, sediments are deposited in the reservoirs that form behind dams. Sand and gravel deposit at the upstream end of reservoirs and form deltas that also extend upstream beyond the full reservoir pool. Clay and silt deposit farther downstream along the reservoir bottom and all the way to the dam. Over time, these sediment deposits build-up to the point where they significantly reduce a reservoir's storage capacity and may prevent the proper function of dam outlets and reservoir water intakes. Without intervention, reservoirs eventually become filled with deposits, which means water is no longer being stored for future use.

Therefore measures must be taken to get rid of the sedimentation of reservoirs. Besides many current measures, this article proposes an innovative way to solve this problem. That is, it is suggested that the reservoir is designed to have 2 parts: sedimentation tank and main body. The sedimentation tank part of the reservoir is used for the incoming water to become clean so that most sedimentation is removed before water enters into main body.

This proposal uses the scientific structure of Tai Chi symbol as a way to minimize the sedimentation. Please refer to figure 1.

A. Shape of Tai Chi symbol (composed of one "yang" fish and one "yin" fish)

B. Shape of "yang" fish symbol

C. Shape of "Yin" fish symbol

Figure 1

And the general layout of the entire reservoir is shown by figure 2

Figure 2

The key feature of the design is as follows:

- The reservoir consists of 2 parts: sedimentation tank and main body. The shape of the reservoir does not have to exactly resemble the shape of Taichi symbol
- Although the shape of Taichi symbol could be a perfect shape for such a reservoir. The essence of the proposal is to build a sedimentation tank that allows the foreign substance in the water to fall down and

separate from water before water enters into the main body of the reservoir. This is, the sedimentation is removed before the water enters into the main body of the reservoir.

- The reservoir main body can be much larger and/or deeper than the sedimentation tank.
- Usually, there should be at least one venting hole in the sedimentation tank. The venting hole(s) in the reservoir main body is (are) optional. Venting holes of sedimentation tank and of the reservoir main body are closed in normal times and will open when there is a need to vent sedimentation and/or water.
- Venting holes are usually located in the low position of the bottom. It is not necessary to always locate the venting holes in the middle of the bottom structure.
- A venting hole can be a hole if the bottom of the structures are manually built. In this case, the hole will be connected to outgoing river through a huge pipe. Or a venting hole can be just the inlet of a huge pipe if the reservoir bottom structures are not man-made.
- The bottom of the Sedimentation tank can be built according to a shape so that the sedimentation will accumulated mainly in the area of the venting hole of sedimentation tank (eye of "yang" fish).
- Additional methods can be used to further remove the sedimentation in the main body of the reservoir and/or in the sedimentation tank to form a comprehensive systematic solution to solve the issue of the sedimentation completely.

As said earlier, the main idea of this proposal is to design the reservoir so that it has 2 parts: main body and sedimentation tank. The additionally designed structure called "sedimentation tank" is used to receive and contain the incoming water from a river and allow the water to stay still and allow the dirt and sand and other foreign matters in the incoming water to subside and separate from the water and fall to the bottom. Then the water will contains much less sedimentation matters and becomes much cleaner. The cleaner water will then flow into the reservoir main body. Because the water is much cleaner than before, the sedimentation will be very much reduced in the reservoir main body.

This proposal is an improvement over the current methods because it is an innovative method. Current methods mainly focus on removing sedimentation from reservoir after sedimentation accumulated in reservoir, while this proposal focus on removing sedimentation before they accumulated in reservoir main body.

The idea of sedimentation tank is actually a rather simple solution. What we need to determine is the rate how fast the sedimentation matters separate from the water to an acceptable standard. Then we will be able to design the sedimentation tank. This proposal involves with simple structure, simple data and simple calculation.

It is apparent that the more muddy the incoming water is, the more serious will the sedimentation accumulation problems be. Thus the Taichi reservoir will play a more important role. It is more necessary to build the sedimentation tank for a reservoir. The Taichi reservoir will be more useful.

The shape of a "yin" fish or "yang" fish in Tai Chi symbol is narrow in one end and wide in the other end. This shape can be useful to build the sedimentation tank. When the water enters sedimentation tank, it goes through a narrow channel, the water flows fast, so there is usually no concern of sedimentation. After water entered the sedimentation tank, the wide shape makes the water flows slowly and becomes relatively still when the sedimentation matters can separate from the water and fall to the bottom of the sedimentation tank. We would need to know how fast the sedimentation matters separate from the water so that we will know how big the sedimentation tank would be.

It may also be necessary to build more than one sedimentation tanks. After the first sedimentation tank is full of the water from incoming river, the entrance of it will be closed so that the water inside sedimentation tank to be fully still and sedimentation matters will separate from water quickly. Then the entrance of the second sedimentation tank will be opened to receive water from the incoming river. How many sedimentation tanks are needed to be built is based upon the rate how fast the sedimentation matters can separate from the water.

Using this approach, most the of sedimentation matters are removed before entering the reservoir main body, so the cost for removing additional sedimentation will be extremely low. The resources and expertise needed to successfully develop this proposed approach about building the sedimentation tank are basic chemical and construction data that are easily acquirable. The cost of the approach is mainly the cost for building the sedimentation tank. A possible additional advantage of this approach is that it allows the water to be purified before entering the main body of the reservoir, so it offers the possibility of treating the water according to relevant needs. For example, for some water source that were not previously for drinking use, it is possible to turn it into drinking water source after being treated in the sedimentation tank with appropriate methods. For example, some harmless chemical may be added to the sedimentation tank to help purify the water.

When we eat food into our stomach, we chew first. According to the same logic, it is naturally reasonable for us to treat water from Incoming river before it enters the main body of the reservoir. After treating, the problem of sedimentation accumulation, along with other possible problems, can be solved. For example, the cost for further removing the sedimentation accumulation in the main body of reservoir will be greatly reduced. Another possible example is that non-drinking water can be turned into drinking water. These apparently have huge commercial values.

The demonstration of the validity of this proposed solution can be accomplished in lab. By simulating the actual environment of the reservoir, data can be provided to prove the validity of this solution. Relevant data can include:

How many percentage of the sedimentation matters can be separate from the water in the sedimentation tank after how long a time. We would prefer that the sedimentation separate quickly from the water.

How big the sedimentation tank needs to be built to contain the incoming water and allow the water to become relatively still and allow the sedimentation matters to separate from the water.

A computerized simulation model can also be built to simulate the process and be used for calculations when determining the structure size according to real water quality and the targets which we want to achieve.

Finally, to document the results of the demonstration, a statistic table can be worked out and used as a guideline to design the sedimentation structure. The table would preferably include such items as incoming water chemical composition, duration of time needed for the foreign matters to separate from the water, and how big the volume would the sedimentation tank be.

Conclusion:

- Taichi reservoir is a reservoir which uses the shape of Taichi as a primary structure. This reservoir structure includes the sedimentation tank and the main body.
- Taichi reservoir can be useful solution in dealing with the sedimentation problem of reservoirs.
- Designing and building Taichi reservoir is neither difficult nor costly.
- Taichi reservoir is more useful when the incoming water of a reservoir contains more sedimentation matters.

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